

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID-ANTIVIRAL ACTIVITY by CPE_VIRUCIDAL CMP
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Version:	01	
Valid from:	06.01.2026	

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1. Goal and Area of Application

When evaluating the antiviral effect of a compound, assessing cellular toxicity in the target cell line is an essential prerequisite (see dedicated SOP). The highest dose allowing > 90 % cell viability is the first tested dose in antiviral assay. SARS-CoV-2, WNV and CHIKV infections on Vero E6 cell line causes a cytopathic effect (CPE) that can be used as a simple, low-cost first-line method for evaluating the antiviral efficacy of compounds.

2. Definitions and Abbreviations

CHIKV	Chikungunya virus
WNV	West Nile Virus
CMPs	Compounds
CPE	Cytopathic effect
DMSO	Dimethylsulfoxide

3. Method

3.1 General

This SOP describes the evaluation of antiviral efficacy of virucidal compounds by visual inspection of cytopathic effect. Virucidal compounds act directly on the virus and are pre-incubated with viruses before cell infection. This technique implies cell infection with a complete virus and therefore requires a BSL-3 facility.

CPE on VeroE6 cells can be observed under a microscope 3 to 5 days post-infection. The CPE can be used to measure the antiviral efficacy of a compound by incubating a constant dose of virus with dilutions of the compound: when the dose is effective to inhibit infection, the cell layer remains intact. When the dose is unable to inhibit infection, the cells die and areas of lysis are observed in the cell layer.

3.2 Information for consumables / chemicals /equipment

Product name	Supplier	Ordering n°
DMEM High Glucose	Gibco	61965059
Fetal Bovine Serum	e.g. Gibco	e.g. 10270-106
Penicillin/Streptomycin	Gibco	15140
DMSO	Sigma	472301
Favipiravir	MCE	HY-14768
Sofosbuvir	Clinisciences	HY-15005
Remdesivir	MCE	HY-104077
Sterile 96 well culture plate, flat bottom (polystyrene)	e.g. Dutscher	e.g. 353072

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SARS-CoV-2 viral stock	In house viral stocks	
WNV viral stock	In house viral stocks	Austria L2 lineage
CHIKV viral stock	In house viral stocks	ECSCA strain P2
VeroE6 cells	Gift from Arbovirus CNR	
Investigational compounds		

EQUIPMENT		
Inverted microscope	e.g. OLYMPUS	e.g. IX50-58F2
3D rotative platform	e.g. FISHERBRAND	e.g. 888861046

3.3 Procedure

3.3.1 Cell seeding (DAY 0)

- Vero E6 cells are seeded 10,000 cells/well in flat bottom 96-well plates, early in the morning
- After 6 hours incubation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ to allow proper adhesion and stabilization, control wells are treated with a control drug that inhibit 100% of viral infection
- * 10 µM of Remdesivir for SARS-CoV-2
- * 50 µM of Sofosbuvir for WNV
- * 100 µM of Favipiravir for CHIKV
- Plates are then incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ for 16h

3.3.2 Virus + compound pre-incubation (DAY 1)

Note : For compounds sensitive to light, tests have to be performed IN DARK CONDITION

- First the initial stock solutions of compounds are diluted to the double of the highest non-toxic concentration in the appropriate medium (including DMSO if needed for compound solubility).
- Then serial 2-fold dilutions are carried out in the appropriate medium.
- For each tested viruses, a viral solution is prepared in DMEM 0% FCS for a final MOI 0.01
- Finally, the viral solutions are mixed 1:1 with the compounds' dilutions to obtain the desired range of concentrations in a final volume of 200µL.
- A 1:1 mix of DMEM 0% FCS and the CMPs dilutions will be used as non-infected, treated control.
- The mixes are incubated 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂

3.3.3 Viral stocks titration (DAY 1)

During (Virus + compound pre-incubation), the viral stocks are titrated

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- Serial 10-fold dilutions of the viral stocks are made in DMEM 0% FCS
- VeroE6 cells are infected with the dilutions from 10^{-2} to 10^{-6} (for SARS-CoV-2 strains titration) or from 10^{-2} to 10^{-9} (for WNV and CHIKV stocks) (8 replicate/dilution)
- The plates are incubated 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂
- Medium is renewed with DMEM 2% FCS and plates are incubated for 3-5 days at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂
- Viral stocks are titrated by counting the number of wells showing a cytopathic effect for each dilution and using the Spearman and Kärber algorithm.

3.3.4 Cells infection (DAY 1)

- VeroE6 cells are treated with the dilutions of viruses + CMP in duplicate wells
 - The plates were incubated 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂
 - Medium is replaced with DMEM 2% FCS
 - Control wells previously treated are also infected for 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂
 - Medium is then replaced by DMEM 2% FCS with control drug (10 µM of Remdesivir for SARS-CoV-2; 50 µM of Sofosbuvir for WNV; 100 µM of Favipiravir for CHIKV)
 - The non-treated control is also infected for 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂. Medium is then replaced by DMEM 2% FCS
 - Non-infected control cells are treated with the CMP diluted with DMEM 0% FCS
- Plates are incubated for 3-5 days at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂

3.3.5 Neutralization evaluation (DAY 3-5)

- Neutralization evaluation is based on cytopathic effect (CPE) observation in the wells.
- Non treated cells are used as the reference of non-neutralized infection with cells showing CPE (indicated by “+” in the report sheet).
- Non-infected control cells and control drug treated cells are used as the reference of neutralized infection with intact cell layer (no CPE, indicated by “-” in the report sheet).

3.3.6 Data analysis and interpretation

Before interpreting the CPE results, it is necessary to ensure that the viral stock titer and the controls are compliant.

1. Check the conformity of the viral stock titer

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The expected viral stock titer (used to calculate the volumes needed for viral suspension) and the read viral stock titer (evaluated during the experiment) should not differ by more than half a log.

2. Check the conformity of the control wells

- * Positive control : the “infected non treated” wells must show a CPE
- * Negative control : the “non infected” wells and the wells treated with control drugs must show an intact cell layer (no CPE)

If the titer and the controls are compliant, then the CPE of the tested drugs can be analysed.

Data analysis - IC50 estimation using binomial logistic regression

Data

Each well gives a binary outcome:

- Positive → virus replicated (infection not inhibited)
- Negative → infection inhibited

For each drug concentration C_i :

- n_i = total wells tested
- x_i = number of positive wells

Model

$$x_i \sim \text{Binomial}(n_i, p_i)$$

$$\text{Logit}(p_i) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \log_{10}(C_i)$$

p_i : probability a well is infected at concentration C_i

β_0, β_1 : regression coefficients

IC50 calculation

$$IC_{50} = 10^{-\beta_0/\beta_1}$$

Concentration at which $pi=0.5$

Bootstrapping to get CIs

For each bootstrap iteration (1000 iterations), the set of (n_i, x_i, C_i) observations were sampled with replacement

Logistic regression was refit to sampled data to obtain IC50 estimates, from which 95% CI was calculated